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ASSESSMENT OF THE CURRENT STATE OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT AT SEAPORTS IN VIETNAM

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Annotation: Environmental management at Vietnamese seaports has basically met the regulations of Vietnamese law on environmental protection. However, other effective aspects of this work such as meeting the regulations of international maritime treaties that Vietnam participates in, enhancing the image of port enterprises in the eyes of the community, partners and stakeholders are still limited. In order for Vietnamese seaports to be able to compete with ports in the region in the context of increasing international and national regulations on pollution control, one of the issues that needs to be studied and implemented is to improve the effectiveness of environmental management at ports. This article analyzes and evaluates the current status of environmental management at Vietnamese seaports. On that basis, some solutions are proposed to improve the effectiveness of this work.

Keywords: seaport, environmental management, sustainable development

ОЦЕНКА ТЕКУЩЕГО СОСТОЯНИЯ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДОЙ В МОРСКИХ ПОРТАХ ВО ВЬЕТНАМЕ

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Аннотация: Управление окружающей средой в морских портах Вьетнама в основном соответствует положениям вьетнамского законодательства об охране окружающей среды. Однако другие эффективные аспекты этой работы, такие как соблюдение положений

международных морских договоров, в которых участвует Вьетнам, повышение имиджа портовых предприятий в глазах общества, партнеров и заинтересованных сторон, по-прежнему ограничены. Для того чтобы вьетнамские морские порты могли конкурировать с портами региона в контексте ужесточения международных и национальных правил по контролю за загрязнением, одним из вопросов, который необходимо изучить и реализовать, является повышение эффективности управления окружающей средой в портах. В данной статье анализируется и оценивается текущее состояние управления окружающей средой в морских портах Вьетнама. На этой основе предлагаются некоторые решения для повышения эффективности этой работы.

Ключевые слова: морской порт, управление окружающей средой, устойчивое развитие

1. Problem statement

The development of seaports in the world has entered the fourth generation, known as green ports or ecological ports. This is a seaport model that aims at sustainable development, minimizing resource waste, enhancing social responsibility and competitive advantage of the port through the implementation of environmental goals and strategies that are fully integrated with the port's development goals and strategies.

The Vietnamese seaport system plays an important role in the country's economy. The management of Vietnamese seaports has achieved many positive results, contributing greatly to socio-economic development. However, there are still difficulties and shortcomings in the seaport management and exploitation model, including environmental management issues. In the context of increasingly deep international integration, in order for Vietnamese seaports to compete fairly with ports in the region and the world, one of the solutions that needs to be implemented is to improve environmental management capacity at ports, aiming at sustainable development. In order to improve environmental management capacity at seaports, analyzing and evaluating the current situation is necessary.

2. Current status and development trends of Vietnam's seaport system

Vietnam has achieved certain results in building and developing the seaport system, forming gateway seaports and specialized seaports in key economic regions, basically meeting the demand for transporting goods by sea, serving the socio-economic development of the country and the demand for exporting goods to countries around the world. The current Vietnamese seaport system consists of 45 seaports, including 02 type IA seaports, 12 type I seaports, 18 type II seaports and 13 type III seaports, with 251 seaports with a total length of about 88,000m of wharf [4]. The volume of goods passing through the port in 2024 will reach 864,223,000 tons.

The planning for the development of the Vietnamese seaport system to 2030, with a vision to 2050, includes 5 groups of seaports with the following cargo handling capacity:

Group 1 of seaports:

By 2030, the volume of goods passing through will be from 322 to 384 million tons (container cargo from 13 to 16 million TEU); passengers from 281 to 302 thousand passengers.

Vision to 2050: meet the demand for goods with an average growth rate of about 5.0 to 5.3%/year; passengers with an average growth rate of about 1.5 to 1.6%/year. Complete investment in Lach Huyen and Cai Lan port areas and relocate ports on Cam River in accordance with the development plan of Hai Phong city; invest in developing ports in Nam Do Son – Van Uc, Cam Pha, Hai Ha port areas.

Group of seaports No. 2:

By 2030, goods will pass through from 182 to 251 million tons (container goods from 0.4 to 0.6 million TEU); passengers from 374 to 401 thousand passengers.

Vision to 2050: meet the demand for goods with an average growth rate of about 3.6 to 4.5%/year; Passenger growth averages from 0.4 to 0.5%/year. Complete investment and development of Nghi Son – Dong Hoi, Vung Ang and Son Duong – Hon La port clusters.

Seaport group No. 3:

By 2030, cargo throughput will be from 160 to 187 million tons (container cargo reaching from 2.5 to 3.1 million TEU, excluding international transit cargo); passengers from 3.4 to 3.9 million passengers.

Vision to 2050: meet the demand for cargo throughput with an average growth rate of about 4.5 to 5.5%/year; passengers average growth

of about 1.7 to 1.8%/year. Complete investment in the entire Lien Chieu port area (Da Nang) and form a port serving international transit cargo in Van Phong (Khanh Hoa).

Group of seaports No. 4:

By 2030, the cargo throughput will be from 500 to 564 million tons (container cargo from 29 to 33 million TEU, excluding international transit cargo); passengers from 2.8 to 3.1 million passengers.

Vision to 2050: meet the demand for cargo throughput with an average growth rate of about 3.5 to 3.8%/year; passengers will grow on average from 0.9 to 1.0%/year. Complete the investment in Cai Mep Ha port, continue to invest in Can Gio international transit port area in Ho Chi Minh City to form a large-scale international transit port cluster of regional and international stature at the Cai Mep estuary (including Cai Mep and Can Gio wharf areas), complete the relocation of ports on the Saigon River and continue to study the relocation of other wharf areas in accordance with the development of Ho Chi Minh City's urban space.

Group of seaports No. 5:

By 2030, cargo throughput will be from 86 to 108 million tons (container cargo from 1.3 to 1.8 million TEU); passengers from 10.5 to 11.2 million passengers.

Vision to 2050: meet the demand for cargo throughput with an average growth rate of about 5.5 to 6.1%; passengers will grow on average from 1.1 to 1.25%. Forming a gateway port for the Mekong Delta region.

3. Analysis and assessment of the current status of environmental management at Vietnamese seaports

The responsibility of seaport enterprises in environmental management is to comply with legal regulations and apply solutions and tools to prevent and minimize environmental pollution.

In the past, although specialized state management at seaports has been well implemented by current agencies and units, meeting management requirements and actual maritime operations. However, the organization and management of seaport exploitation have not kept up with advanced management models in the world, have not been really effective and still have shortcomings and problems. Environmental management at Vietnamese seaports currently has overlapping functions and tasks, lacks concentration, lacks unity and is constrained by vertical and horizontal management and operation relationships. Regarding state management at

seaports, from top to bottom, there are: Ministry of Construction – Vietnam Maritime Administration – Maritime Port Authority. According to this system, at the port authority level, there is no specialized unit for environmental protection. Regarding environmental management at the local level, from lower to higher levels, there are: Provincial People's Committee – Department of Agriculture and Environment – Department of Environmental Management. At the environmental management level at seaport enterprises, at most seaports, this work has not been separated, and there are even no specialized staff.

Thus, at the local level and port enterprises, environmental management has not been implemented as a specialized task, leading to difficulties in coordinating environmental management and protection with other local authorities such as the Department of Agriculture and Environment, and the Department of Environmental Management.

Regarding port enterprises, although there have been many efforts in environmental management, there are still shortcomings and limitations such as enterprises that do not have sufficient environmental records according to the provisions of law and do not have environmental policies. Survey data on the current status of environmental management at Vietnamese seaports and wharves show that: The number of ports and wharves with ISO 14000 certificates is 37 out of 152 surveyed units; 127 out of 152 units have environmental impact assessment approval decisions; 69 out of 152 have discharge licenses; 32 out of 152 have hazardous waste treatment licenses; 110 out of 152 have oil spill response plans; 122 out of 152 have periodic environmental monitoring [2]. The issues of unclear coordination and coordination between local units and the lack of specialized environmental departments as mentioned above, some prominent environmental issues have appeared in ports and seaport areas as follows:

1. Pressure on aquatic ecosystems in port areas such as increased turbidity, changes in hydrological regime, pollution of seabed sediments and seawater due to dredging of port channels and dumping of dredged materials. This impact occurs in most port areas.

2. Increase in environmental pollutants such as oil, grease, heavy metal ores, pesticides, fertilizers, toxic gases, dust, etc. due to the dispersion of cargo at the port.

3. Odor pollution, reduced water clarity, reduced dissolved oxygen in water causing death or reduced growth of aquatic species due to dumping of waste from ships.

4. Noise pollution, water pollution due to toxic substances in ship paint, dust and other chemicals due to building and repairing new ships.

5. Causing noise, air pollution due to exhaust fumes, dust and unpleasant odors from freight, container and ship traffic.

6. Increasing the most serious pollutants in port waters due to oil and chemical spills, the impacts of which have been mentioned in many works.

7. Fires and explosions often occur in warehouses, especially those containing oil, chemicals and flammable materials. Fires and explosions not only destroy property and people but also cause environmental disasters such as oil spills, chemicals, dust and smoke as well as hydrocarbons that pollute the air.

Due to the characteristics of the maritime industry in general and seaports in particular, the environmental management of port enterprises must not only comply with Vietnamese laws but also comply with environmental protection regulations in international treaties to which Vietnam is a member. Currently, Vietnam has joined 21 international treaties on maritime, including many treaties related to environmental pollution prevention such as: United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea 1982 (UNCLOS 82), International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL 73/78)... One of the obligations of a member state when joining any convention is to be prepared in terms of laws, technology and human resources to meet the requirements of that convention. The government of a member state must incorporate the requirements of the convention into its domestic law. However, so far, treaties on environmental protection in maritime and seaport operations have not been fully internalized. Currently, the number of specific regulations on the responsibilities of seaports in meeting international environmental conventions in the maritime sector that Vietnam has joined is still small.

4. Solutions for environmental management at seaports

To develop Vietnam's seaport system towards sustainable development, it is necessary to implement the following solutions:

1. Build and perfect the legal system on environmental protection specifically applicable to seaports, focusing on internalizing environmental protection regulations in international maritime treaties to which Vietnam is a member.

2. It is necessary to establish a unified port management agency. Most of Vietnam's seaports are currently small in scale, so they do not have the capacity to invest in environmental protection infrastructure such as equipment for collecting and treating waste and toxic substances. To solve this problem, it is necessary to establish a unified port management agency to guide overall management and exploitation in accordance with port planning and adjust and expand when necessary, ensuring efficiency in seaport exploitation, focusing resources on building infrastructure for receiving and treating waste in port clusters.

3. Improve capacity to prevent environmental incidents through establishing a database on incidents, developing plans to prevent and respond to environmental incidents.

5. Conclusion

Environmental management at Vietnamese seaports has achieved positive results in recent times. In order for Vietnamese seaports to develop in a sustainable manner, in the coming time, this work needs to be implemented synchronously to both meet the regulations of Vietnamese law and meet the regulations on environmental protection at seaports according to the regulations of international conventions to which Vietnam is a member.

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